

LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF FOOD-RELATED PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *It is clear from this article to explore the linguocultural features like characteristics of food-related terminologies and their phraseological units in both Uzbek and English languages. The main structure of the study to focus on the semantic features and their structure, figurative meanings and cultural connotations of idiomatic expressions which closely contains food components. The main part is given to the role of phraseological units which reflects the national identity, social studies and cultural value of both nations like Uzbek and English.*

Additionally, the research analyses various English idioms like “piece of cake”, “easy as pie”, “spill the beans” and we can find the comparative points of Uzbek language idioms like “non sindirmoq”, “tuzini ichmoq”, “oshini bermoq”, “nonga moy surgandek”. As nearly all of these idioms are close to each other, the most part of the both nations use them in their daily conversation routines.

The study also examines the transformation of food names into metaphorical and symbolic expressions with the system of phraseological system.

The study also examines the transformation of literal food names into metaphorical and symbolic expressions within phraseological systems. It is clear from the article that, findings about food-related phraseological units can function as not only linguistic elements but also as cultural markers which represents the worldview and historical experiences of current nations. As a result of the research linguacultural studies can develop the phraseological and comparative units by highlighting the real relationships between the languages, culture and national mentality of both nations.

Keywords: *phraseological units, linguacultural analysis, food-related idioms, cultural semantics, connotation, English language, Uzbek language, comparative linguistics.*

INTRODUCTION

Admittedly, the language is not only the means of communication but also the reflection of particular nation's culture, their traditions, worldview and their historical experiences. In today's modern linguistic field, the units like phraseological are considered as one of the most expressive layers of the language and its usage, since this process preserves the cultural information and represents the national identity of the both languages figurative meanings. As Edward Sapir, “Language and culture are closely interconnected, and linguistic units often reflect the social and cultural life of a community” (Sapir, 1921). As it is stated, in modern linguistics, phraseological units and idioms are considered one of the most expressive layers of language since they carry cultural information and cover national identity through figurative meanings.

Furthermore, phraseological units which occupy food-related meaning are occupied very special place in both languages like English and Uzbek. On account of term food is closely connected with everyday life, social relations and cultural traditions, the idioms which contains

food names often acquire the symbol of metaphorical meaning. According to Anna Wierzbicka, “Cultural meanings are deeply closed in lexical and phraseological systems, especially in units related to everyday human experience.” (Wierzbicka, 1997). All of these phraseological units reflects the attitudes of people, their beliefs and moral value of the nations’ cultural perceptions. In modern English linguistic field, food related terms and idioms like “piece of cake” or “spill the beans” are widely used in their daily routines and daily communications.

Similarly, we can find these kind of food related idioms in Uzbek language also, besides Uzbeks use these phraseological units in their daily communication. In my opinion, the main reason of usage these kind of phraseological units are closely connected with their specific connotations. As V. A. Maslova stated that “Linguocultural units preserve national mentality and cultural memory within language structure”, (Maslova, 2001). Despite of the fact that, phraseology and linguocultural studies have been widely discussed by many scholars, and the learners of the field, comparative research focusing specifically on food-related phraseological termins in both languages remains relatively limited. Consequently, this article aims to analyse the linguacultural and features of food-related phraseological units in both languages through semantic and comparative approaches. In Uzbek, the expressions like “non sindirmoq”, “tuzini ichmoq”, “nonga yog’ surgandek” reflect loyalty, respectfulness, hospitality and social relationships in Uzbek culture and its heritage.

According to V. N. Teliya “Phraseology distributes the cultural worldview of a nation which reflects historical and social consciousness through figurative language (Teliya, 1996). The main objective aim of the research is to find out how food-related idioms reflect cultural values, national mentality, and linguistic worldviews in English and Uzbek languages.

MATERIALS

It is clear that, the research can explore and identify the phraseological units and idiomatic expressions which containing food names in English and Uzbek languages. In both languages dictionaries, explanatory dictionaries and academic sources are widely used to explore the most used food related terms. The phraseological units are mostly collected from *Oxford Dictionary of English Idioms*, *Cambridge Idioms Dictionary*, and Kunin’s phraseological dictionary in English language, while Uzbek examples were taken from *O‘zbek tilining frazeologik lug‘ati* by Sh. Rahmatullayev and *O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati*. The study focuses on frequently used phraseological units that contain food-related lexical components and possess cultural and figurative meanings in both languages.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Different kind of linguistic methods were applied while making the research process. Since the main reason is to investigate the linguacultural points and features of various terms which are food-related in both English and Uzbek languages.

The *descriptive method* was used in order to collect and identify phraseological terms by containing food-related names. This method is very suitable for identifying their lexical composition and general semantic characteristics.

Additionally, the *semantic analysis method* was applied for examining the figurative meanings, connotative aspects, and semantic transformations of phraseological expressions. Special attention was paid to the transition of food names from literal meanings to metaphorical and symbolic interpretations.

The comparative method was also very helpful for identifying the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek phraseological units. Through comparative analysis, the cultural and national peculiarities reflected in idiomatic expressions were examined.

Additionally, *the linguacultural approach* played a very important role in displaying phraseological units as cultural markers which are connected with traditions, mentality, and social values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is clear that, the research analysis food related terms in both languages like English and Uzbek. And this process is strong displays in linguacultural significance of these languages. Food related names are transformed into symbolic expressions which can reflect cultural value and social attitudes of the languages.

As an example, the English idioms like “piece of cake” and “easy as pie” identifies the simplicity and convenience of the culture. In these phraseological units, sweet food products symbolize pleasure and positive emotions in evaluation. All of the food related terms reflect the tendency of English culture and their current conversations associating with comfortless and enjoyment with desserts.

Another English idiom, “spill the beans,” reveals the meaning of a secret or disclosing hidden information. Since the lexical component “beans” accordingly refers to food, the expression has acquired a figurative meaning through historical and cultural development.

Additionally, in Uzbek language food related terms express the social respect and loyalty along with hospitality. For example, the phraseological units like “non sindirmoq” symbolizes friendship and respectfulness with sincerity. Like other nations, bread expresses a sacred position of Uzbek culture and associated with blessing and prosperity.

Similarly, the expression “tuzini ichmoq” displays loyalty, gratitude, and moral responsibility. Like the word bread, salt has historically symbolized trust and faithfulness in social relationships within Uzbek culture. That’s why, salt and bread are one of the most used phraseological units in different nations language capacity.

The comparative analysis identifies that English food-related phraseological terms mostly used to express the practicality, simplicity, and emotional evaluation, whereas Uzbek idioms are more closely connected with ethical values, hospitality, and interpersonal relationships.

Therefore, phraseological units containing food names serve as crucial linguistic and cultural markers identifying national mentality and cultural identity.

CONCLUSION

The current study investigated the linguacultural features of food-related phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages. The research analysis showed that phraseological units which contains food components function not only as linguistic expressions but also as crucial carriers of cultural meanings and national values.

The findings express that English and Uzbek food-related idioms express various aspects of cultural worldview and social experience. English phraseological units mainly emphasize simplicity, practicality, and emotional evaluation, while Uzbek expressions are more strongly associated with hospitality, respect, loyalty, and moral traditions.

Additionally, the research confirmed that food-related phraseological units serve as cultural memory and reflect the historical and social development of a nation. Their semantic and connotative structures find out the close relationship between language and culture, nation and notion.

As a results of the study may contribute to extra research in phraseology, linguacultural studies, comparative linguistics, and intercultural communication.

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